

Transparent and Voluntary Government, thanks to the Blockchain

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Abstract

1. Introduction

Introducing the Blockchain into government is a no-brainer. In fact, Dubai announced in 2016 that all government transactions would be on public ledgers by 2030. Public ledgers are a key component of the Blockchain. Given its transparency, the Blockchain would have the ability to provide full transparency to government operations while, to a large extent, maintaining the anonymity of individual users. It also provides the possibility for the government to introduce micro-transaction at minimal cost, opening the door for crowdfunding special infrastructure projects or one time programs, avoiding the need to borrow large amounts, and helping bringing public spending back under control.

2. Discussion

Many people have only started noticing this technology called the Blockchain in the last year or so thanks to Bitcoin's phenomenal rise to the top spot of the hot topics ranking. While the perception of Bitcoin is mixed at best, its underlying technology, the Blockchain, is revolutionary to say the least. In a nutshell, because the information stored in the Blockchain is completely decentralised, it cannot be tampered with. This means that from a data validity perspective, there is simply nothing as reliable. As a result, all industries that exist today with the purpose of authenticating data stand to be disrupted extensively, the money transfer function of banks is already going through that transition, and the real estate market, the health data market and other data intensive intermediary services where data integrity is key, are also likely to change at a fundamental level once the blockchain is introduced into these industries. The government is no exception.

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3. Conclusions

This presentation will explore other ways that Blockchain technology and Cryptocurrencies can be used in government to provide an dramatically more transparent government and perhaps even the transition from a tax based government budgetary system to one where voluntary donations could form the largest part of the government budget.

Author biography

Stephane-Enric Beaulieu Stephane-Enric Beaulieu is a former Diplomate and Executive of the Canadian Department of Foreign Affairs and International Trade. After retiring from Government in 2014, he remained in Japan where he launched an e-commerce start-up focussing on making foreign products and services available to Japanese consumers. Having worked extensively in the video gaming industry while serving as a Trade Commissioner, he borrowed ideas from both e-commerce, the video game industry and leveraged his government expertise to develop the Kaso dApp concepts. He launched Kasolutions in April 2018 in Québec, Canada, where the landscape for Smart-City related technology implementation is one of the most advanced in the world